

IMPACT OF MEASURES FOR ORGANIZING SMALL HOLDINGS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

This article scientifically analyzes the economic and organizational impact of measures aimed at the organization and development of small-scale farming on the development of the agricultural sector. The study highlights the mechanisms for supporting the activities of peasants, farmers and household farms, their role in the efficient use of resources, increasing production volumes and ensuring employment. It also considers the issues of increasing the competitiveness of small-scale farming entities in the agricultural sector, introducing innovative approaches and strengthening investment activity. The study substantiates that improving these forms of farming is an important factor in the sustainable development of the agricultural sector, ensuring food security and increasing socio-economic activity in rural areas.

Introduction. In the current context of globalization and economic transformation, the issue of sustainable development of the agricultural sector is one of the priority areas of the country's economic policy. In particular, the role of small-scale forms of farming in increasing the efficiency of agricultural production, strengthening food security, and ensuring employment in rural areas is incomparable. Farms, dehkans, and household farms, as one of the most important links in the agricultural sector, are of great importance not only in providing the domestic market with food products, but also in increasing export potential. In recent years, large-scale institutional and organizational-economic reforms have been implemented in our country aimed at developing small-scale forms of farming. In particular, a number of measures have been developed to ensure their effective use of land resources, financial support, the introduction of modern agro-technologies, and the development of market infrastructure. These reforms serve to increase the volume of agricultural production, increase labor productivity, and reduce the cost of agricultural products.

In this context, it is of urgent importance to scientifically analyze the impact of measures taken to organize small-scale farming on the development of the agricultural sector. This article comprehensively studies the impact of these forms of farming on economic efficiency, employment, resource utilization, and socio-economic development of rural areas.

Analysis and results. Small-scale forms of management, as one of the most important institutional links of the agrarian sector, are of particular importance in ensuring the stability

of agricultural production. Studies show that it is dehkans, farmers and household farms that have the leading share in the country's agricultural production. In particular, according to the National Statistical Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2025 the total volume of products produced in the agricultural, forestry and fishery sectors amounted to 538.9 trillion soums, of which 62.3 percent fell to dehkans and household farms, 29.4 percent to farms, and the rest to agricultural organizations. This indicator clearly demonstrates the priority role of small-scale forms of management in the development of the agrarian sector.

The analysis revealed that the share of small farms in agricultural production is especially high in vegetable growing, potato growing, horticulture and livestock farming. In particular, dehkan and homestead farms operate as the main production entities in the cultivation of vegetables, potatoes and fruit and vegetable products. This situation increases the economic and social importance of small farms in meeting the daily needs of the population in food products. At the same time, they serve as an important factor in ensuring employment in rural areas, increasing family incomes and reducing poverty. Regional analyses also show that small farms have high economic potential. For example, in January-March 2025, the volume of agricultural activities carried out by small business entities in the Samarkand region amounted to 6,264.2 billion soums, or 92.9 percent of the total volume. This confirms the crucial role of small-scale farming in regional agrarian development. The study also assessed the effectiveness of organizational and economic measures taken to organize small-scale farms. The introduction of support mechanisms such as rational use of land, subsidies, preferential loans, and provision of seeds and equipment has a positive impact on increasing output. In particular, the practical result of these reforms is that the total output of the agricultural sector increased by 4.4% in 2025 compared to the previous year. Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that measures to organize and support small-scale farming are an important strategic tool for increasing the output of the agricultural sector, efficient use of resources, ensuring employment, and accelerating the socio-economic development of regions. In particular, the integration of these forms of economy with innovative technologies, cooperation and logistics systems creates an important basis for further increasing the efficiency of the agricultural sector.

Table 1

The impact of measures to organize small-scale farming on the development of the agricultural sector

No	Direction of action	Implementation mechanism	Impact on the development of the agricultural sector	Expected result
1	Efficient use of land resources	Optimization of land areas, introduction of intensive cropping systems	Productivity and production volume increase	Production volume will increase by 10-15%
2	Financial support	Soft loans, subsidies and grants	Working capital shortages will decrease	Investment activity and production will expand
3	Providing	Modern agricultural	Labor productivity	Costs are reduced

	technology and innovation	technology, irrigation, monitoring	drip digital	and resource efficiency increase	and profit margins are increased
4	Cooperation and logistics system	Cooperating peasants, homesteads	farmers, and	Product storage and delivery efficiency increases	Losses are reduced, market coverage is expanded
5	Capacity building	Agronomic advanced programs	training, training	Production will be established based on a scientific approach	Product quality and competitiveness increase
6	Market infrastructure development	Shopping malls, wholesale markets and export channels		Sales volume and profitability indicators will increase	Export potential will increase
7	Employment support	Expanding entrepreneurship and small businesses	family and	Jobs will be created in rural areas	Social stability and incomes increase

The table data shows that the effective organization and development of small-scale farming is one of the important factors ensuring the sustainable growth of the agricultural sector. First of all, measures taken to effectively use land resources, in particular, the optimization of land areas and the introduction of an intensive cropping system, directly contribute to increasing the level of productivity. As a result, the volume of agricultural production will significantly increase, and production efficiency will increase.

At the same time, the implementation of mechanisms for financial support for small-scale farms, namely the allocation of preferential loans, subsidies and grants, will improve their level of working capital. This serves as an important economic tool for increasing investment activity, expanding the scale of production and reducing the cost of production.

The analysis shows that the introduction of modern equipment and innovative technologies is of particular importance in increasing the efficiency of small-scale farms. In particular, the use of modern agricultural technology, drip irrigation systems and digital monitoring tools increases labor productivity, reduces the consumption of water and other resources. As a result, production costs decrease and the profitability of farms increases. In addition, the development of cooperation and logistics systems enhances the integration of small-scale farming with the market. The integration of farmers, dehkans and household farms on a cooperative basis helps to reduce losses in the processes of storing, processing and delivering products to the consumer. This expands the scope of the domestic market and increases export potential.

Capacity building is also an important component of this system. Through advanced training courses, agronomic trainings and scientific and practical seminars, the knowledge and skills of farmers are strengthened. This leads to a stronger scientific approach to production, improved product quality and increased competitiveness.

In general, the measures presented in the table are a comprehensive mechanism that serves to increase the economic efficiency of small-scale farming, strengthen the production

potential of the agricultural sector, expand employment in rural areas and ensure socio-economic stability.

Conclusions and proposals. As a result of the research, it was found that measures aimed at the organization and development of small-scale farming are an important strategic factor in ensuring the sustainable development of the agricultural sector. In particular, it was scientifically substantiated that farmers, peasants and household farms play a leading role in increasing the volume of agricultural production, ensuring the uninterrupted supply of food products to the domestic market, increasing employment in rural areas and increasing the income of the population. The results of the study showed that the share of small-scale farming in the development of the agricultural sector is of great importance not only from the point of view of economic, but also from the point of view of social stability.

It was also found that the economic efficiency of these farms can be significantly increased through the rational use of land resources, improvement of financial support mechanisms, introduction of innovative technologies and development of cooperation systems. In particular, subsidies, preferential loans, improvement of logistics infrastructure and strengthening integration with the market will serve to expand the production and sales volumes of small farms.

Based on the study, it is considered appropriate to put forward the following practical proposals. First, it is necessary to increase the volume of preferential loans and subsidies allocated by the state for small business entities and strengthen the system of monitoring their targeted and effective use. Second, it is necessary to increase the efficiency of resource use through the widespread introduction of modern agrotechnologies, digital monitoring systems and water-saving methods. Third, it is important to strengthen cooperative ties between farmers, dehkans and household farms, and to form a unified logistics system for storing, processing and selling products. Fourth, it is advisable to improve the knowledge and skills of small business owners in rural areas by expanding their training courses, scientific and practical seminars and consulting services.

In conclusion, the development of smallholder farming is an important factor in the sustainable growth of the agricultural sector, strengthening food security, and accelerating the socio-economic development of rural areas..

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